

Economic assessment of single-cell protein production for cheese whey valorization by purple phototrophic bacteria

A. Remelli*, A. Amini*, V. Mojarad* M. Achkar*, A. Turolla*

* Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Polytechnic of Milan, Leonardo Da Vinci Square 32, Milan, 20133, IT (E-mail: andrea.remelli@polimi.it)

Abstract

Agriculture is a major contributor to climate change, accounting for approximately 11% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and generating substantial amounts of food waste. Cheese whey (CW), a significant by-product of the dairy industry, offers a promising opportunity for resource valorization, contributing to the mitigation of agri-food system impacts and the development of circular value chains capable of replacing unsustainable products. This study assesses the economic feasibility of converting CW into single-cell protein (SCP) through an integrated process combining acidogenic fermentation and cultivation of purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB). Experimental and modelling results show a 75% conversion efficiency during acidogenic fermentation and stable PPB biomass production on fermented CW. This valorization pathway could potentially reduce production costs to as low as €5 per kilogram of biomass, achieving a protein productivity per hectare four times higher than that of soybean meal.

Keywords

Agri-food systems; circular economy; dairy industry; phototrophic microorganisms; sustainable bioprocesses; techno-economic analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The world is facing a critical challenge, as 2024 marked the first year in which the average global temperature exceeded 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels (Tollefson, 2025). Agriculture plays a significant role in climate change, acting as a major emitter of methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) (Lynch et al., 2021). These gases account for 42% and 75% of global CH₄ and N₂O emissions, respectively, highlighting the inefficiency of resource utilization within agricultural systems (FAOSTAT, 2020). Overall, agriculture contributes approximately 11% of total global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Smith et al., 2007).

Furthermore, agriculture is both a driver and a victim of climate change. Water demand, availability, and utilization are significantly influenced by the intensification of the global water cycle (Huntington, 2006), making efficient agricultural production planning and land management increasingly vital (Tao et al., 2003).

The agricultural sector is also responsible for an estimated 1.4 billion tonnes of food loss and waste annually, with roughly one-third of the protein produced globally never reaching consumers (Beuving et al., 2024). Despite this inefficiency, 11% of the world's population remains undernourished (Prosekov & Ivanova, 2018). Among the major contributors to food waste, cheese production generates approximately 160.7 million m³ of cheese whey (CW) per year, characterized by high organic loads — with a chemical oxygen demand (COD) of about 50 g L⁻¹, nitrogen (N) ranging from 0.2 to 1.8 kg m⁻³, and phosphorus (P) from 0.12 to 0.54 kg m⁻³ (de Almeida et al., 2023).

Currently, anaerobic digestion (AD) is the most widely applied and mature biotechnology for resource recovery in the agri-food sector (He et al., 2023). However, innovative biorefinery approaches are emerging as promising alternatives, enabling the conversion of fermentation products into high-value microbial biomass (Capson-Tojo et al., 2020; He et al., 2023). Among these, the production of microbial biomass for food and feed applications stands out, as it allows valuable nutrients to be retained within the food chain rather than diverted to lower-value uses such as energy recovery or landfill disposal (de Almeida et al., 2023; Delamare-Deboutteville et al., 2019; Hülsen et al., 2018),

which can pose environmental risks (de Almeida et al., 2023).

Purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) have attracted increasing attention in the scientific community for their potential in resource recovery (Areniello et al., 2023; Capson-Tojo et al., 2020; George et al., 2020; Hülsen et al., 2018). Within the framework of the circular economy and biorefinery concepts, PPB offer a pathway toward improved resource efficiency. A particularly promising application involves the upcycling of cheese whey into single-cell protein (SCP), providing a means to valorize an underutilized resource (Arias et al., 2023). This strategy not only reduces dependence on conventional protein sources but also enhances nutrient recovery and improves overall nutritional quality (Delamare-Deboutteville et al., 2019; Hülsen et al., 2018).

The present study conducts a techno-economic assessment of cheese whey recovery and its conversion into SCP to evaluate whether this approach represents a viable and sustainable solution to food waste, while contributing to a more resilient and efficient agricultural system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An economic evaluation was conducted to assess the feasibility of SCP production for feed integration and to reduce dependence on soybean meal as a high-protein source. The overall production capacity of the system was calculated accordingly. The valorization process layout is illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Valorization process layout: (1) cheese whey tank, (2) CSTR for CW acidification, (3) ultrafiltration (UF) unit for volatile fatty acid (VFA) recovery from fermented broth, (4a/4b) PBR for PPB cultivation – two configurations for were assessed (flat-plate vs. raceway pond). Two downstream processes to produce protein powder were compared: ultrafiltration (5a) combined with spray drying (6a), centrifuge (5b) combined with freeze drying (6b).

Water recirculation was assumed after each solid–liquid separation step, while the performances of acidogenic fermentation and PPB cultivation productivity were derived from laboratory experiments. The acidogenic bioreactor consisted of a 10 L continuous stirred-tank reactor (CSTR) operated at organic loading rate (OLR) of $6 \text{ g COD L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$, hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 2 days, and temperature of $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The photobioreactor (PBR) was a 10-L flat-plate reactor operated in sequencing batch mode (SBR) with an OLR of $3 \text{ g COD L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$, an HRT of 4 days, and a temperature of $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The flat-plate surface was covered with a light-filtering film allowing only infrared irradiation ($\lambda = 850 \text{ nm}$) to reach the cultivation medium. A total production period of 8 months was modelled. All equipment operational parameters were obtained from industrial machine vendors' catalogues.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system is designed to produce a protein-rich powder for use as substitute ingredient for conventional protein sources in the livestock farming. Acidogenic fermentation was demonstrated as an effective biotechnological process for converting carbohydrate-rich streams into VFAs under stable conditions, achieving a conversion rate of 75% (Figure 2a). The PBR provided a suitable configuration for PPB cultivation, which can be optimized and operated in a semi-continuous mode. The system was capable of producing a stable biomass concentration in the effluent (Figure 2b).

Figure 2a: VFA proportion and degree of acidification of cheese whey fermentation in anaerobic SBR.

Figure 2b: Biomass concentration in PBR effluent over 24 days.

The estimated production costs for the system configurations are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: PPB production cost (€/kg of biomass) in four different configurations after ultrafiltration step to recover VFAs: (A) flat-plate PBR, centrifuge and freeze dryer, (B) flat-plate PBR, ultrafiltration and spray dryer, (C) raceway pond, centrifuge and freeze dryer, (D) raceway pond, ultrafiltration and spray dryer.

The valorization process is capable of producing a protein-rich powder with 5% moisture content and 60% protein inclusion, achieving a biomass productivity per hectare four times higher than that of traditional protein sources. Electricity consumption represents the dominant contributor to production costs, making both thermal and electrical efficiency critical for optimizing performance. Production costs are directly influenced by the type of photobioreactor and solid–liquid separation technology employed, both of which affect the quality control of the final product. Specifically, production using flat-plate PBRs is 27% more expensive than with raceway ponds, due to their more complex design and higher material costs. Conversely, the solid–liquid separation method combining ultrafiltration and spray drying is 20% cheaper than centrifugation followed by freeze-drying, owing to its greater treatment capacity and energy efficiency. The process can yield up to 25 kg of biomass per cubic meter of cheese whey processed. Overall, the system is water-neutral compared to soybean meal production, which requires 35.4 L of water per kilogram of product (Chesterfield, 2024).

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